

Adverse temperature tolerance

Varietal screening for cold tolerance

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Rainfed rice cultivation in Sikkim extends from 300 m to 2,000 m. In general, 80% or more of the rice area is occupied by local traditional varieties with good grain quality, blast resistance, and cold tolerance. They are of long duration and have low yields. The season for transplanting depends on the onset of the monsoon. Improved varieties that have been adopted are of short duration with high yields and average grain quality, but are not cold tolerant.

Improved varieties DR92, Rassi, and Prasad were compared with local

varieties Thapachine, Krishanbhog, Champasare, Tulasi, Dutkati, and Sarju 49 for cold tolerance under field and glasshouse conditions. Average minimum temperature after 15 Nov was 8-14 °C under both conditions. In addition, tap water irrigation at 5-10 °C was given in the glasshouse.

Pollen production and viability in some rice varieties under cold temperature. Sikkim, India.

Genotype	Field condition		Glasshouse condition		Normal condition ^a
	Pollen count	Viability (%)	Pollen count	Viability (%)	Viability (%)
Sarju 49	Very low	33.5	Very low	3.9	82.9
DR92	Very low	40.7	Very low	22.4	92.5
Prasad	Very low	35.5	Very low	15.7	67.8
Rassi	Very low	35.7	Very low	15.5	80.4
Thapachine	Low	50.7	Low	38.8	82.2
Krishanbhog	Low	45.5	Low	35.6	84.4
Champasare	Low	49.5	Very low	28.7	85.8
Dutkati	Low	50.0	Very low	28.5	78.7
Tulasi	Average	60.7	Low	48.9	90.3
Khosaro	Low	34.6	Very low	12.7	84.7

^aPollen count was normal.

Low temperature and cold water were observed to affect spikelet emergence and development. Chlorophyll degradation was also observed.

Pollen production and pollen viability were much higher in traditional varieties than in improved varieties (see table). Chlorophyll degradation was also faster in cold-susceptible cultivars. Low water temperature in the glasshouse resulted in lower pollen count and viability. □

Screening rice varieties for cold tolerance at early seedling stage

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In the hill zone of North India, about 1.8 million ha of rice is exposed to low temperature damage at different growth stages. The Mar- or Apr-sown crop in the medium and higher altitudes and the boro crops in the West Bengal and Assam plains suffer from low temperature damage at sowing and early seedling stages.

We screened 11 promising indica varieties for cold tolerance at the early seedling stage. In the procedure, 50 uniform seeds of each variety were soaked in water for 24 h in petri dishes, drained, washed thoroughly with distilled water, then covered with moist paper towels and kept at room

Cold tolerance at early seedling stage of 11 indica rice varieties in North India hills.

Variety	Seedling survival (%)	Cold tolerance score ^a
VL 191	87	3
T3	76	3
Mahsuri	76	3
VL 206	68	5
Rasi	67	5
IR8	60	5
Govind	37	7
UPRI 82-42	7	7
Pant Dhan 4	6	7
Saket 4	0	9
Prasad	0	9

^a1 = all seedlings with green leaves, 3 = less than 30% of seedlings dead, 5 = 30-50% of seedlings dead, 7 = more than 50% seedlings dead, and 9 = all seedlings dead.

temperature for 3 d. Germinated seeds were submerged in water in petri dishes and refrigerated at 4 °C for 10 d.

After 10 d the petri dishes were removed from the refrigerator. The seeds were kept at room temperature for 1 d, placed in sunlight for 5 d, then scored for cold tolerance.

No variety was completely tolerant. T3, Mahsuri, and VL 191 scored 3 (see table); however, T3 and Mahsuri are not suitable for hill planting because of their long duration (135 d). VL 206, recommended for Mar or Apr sowing in the hills, and Rasi and IR8 scored 5. Other varieties had poor seedling survival. □

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